

Towards a Toolkit for Socio-technical Process Modelling in Agriculture: a Pilot Study

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Abstract—Digital technologies are transforming agriculture, affecting social, institutional, economic, environmental, and technological dimensions. To ensure sustainable development, it is essential to anticipate these impacts and create conditions for sustainable change. Living Labs (LLs) concept facilitates this by involving various stakeholders in co-designing solutions. This paper presents a socio-technical process modelling method using Model-driven requirements engineering (MoDRE) techniques. It employs UML class diagrams, iStar diagrams, and BPMN diagrams to model process structures, goals, and flows. The method, part of the Horizon Europe project CODECS, involves data collection, diagram design, and iterative feedback, tested in a precision irrigation pilot study in Tuscany. Preliminary results demonstrate the method’s effectiveness in supporting interdisciplinary teams, fostering better communication, and aiding in the analysis of digitalisation impacts on agricultural processes. Furthermore, the discussion with stakeholders allowed the fine-tuning of the models and enriched the method for co-creating the diagrams with a toolkit composed of a set of guidelines for eliciting process-relevant information from LLs, a checklist and a detailed procedure for graphical representation.

Index Terms—socio-technical process modelling, digitalisation, MoDRE, agriculture

I. INTRODUCTION

The introduction of digital technologies in agriculture brings radical transformation at multiple levels, such as social, institutional, economic, environmental, and technological [11]. Rijswijk et al. [15] stress the importance of anticipating the impacts of digitalisation and of setting conditions for a successful digital transformation in line with the sustainable development goals. Furthermore, recent studies promote interdisciplinary approaches when developing innovative solutions for agriculture [16] and consider the impacts of the adoption of digital technologies in rural contexts [9]–[11]. According to Beaudoin et al. [6], Living Labs (LLs) discussing environmental sustainability have promising potential in the design and evaluation of services that meet users’ and societal needs. LLs are communities of local practices, including farmers, knowledge intermediaries, stakeholders, and policymakers carrying out co-design activities to address emerging challenges [12].

In such a context, we present our work that proposes a method for socio-technical process modelling to support interdisciplinary teams in the evaluation of the impacts of digitalisation in agriculture. The aim is to support the teams, through standard and easy-to-read representations, in mitigating communication issues due to the stakeholders’ different backgrounds and interests. The representations we propose are graphical models based on model-driven requirements engineering techniques (MoDRE) [5], which leverage diagrammatic notations to represent various aspects of systems requirements, e.g. functionalities, structure, goals, data, processes, and workflows. The method is under development and testing in the HE CODECS (*Maximizing the co-benefits of agricultural digitalisation through conducive digital ecosystems*) research project [1], and is being used in 20 European LLs dealing with the introduction of digital solutions in different agricultural contexts. In CODECS, the objective of process modelling is to provide a comprehensive representation of the transformation in a business process after the introduction of digital technology. Such a representation should be as clear and representative as possible to all stakeholders in the LL, and should support further work, such as a cost-benefit analysis.

The main challenge ahead is the design of such models while contemporary striving for notations to be as standard as possible. The procedure for the development of the models must be in line with project requirements and expectations such as coordinating the data collection with other activities carried out in CODECS and limiting the number of interactions with the LLs. Towards this objective, our approach is based on multiple interactions with the multidisciplinary project consortium to develop a method in the form of a toolkit, to be used by non-experts in the notation and possibly mature enough for an easy and rapid adoption in multiple contexts.

In previous studies, we provided an overview of the proposed method [14] and conducted a first evaluation of its applicability in a co-design context [13]. The current paper presents an additional pilot study carried out in the context of a LL external to the project as further systematic testing of the method. The objective of the LL has been the evaluation of

costs and benefits of a precision irrigation system in orchards. We highlight the three main objectives of this work: i) fine-tuning the models to achieve clear and effective representations; ii) encouraging the use of standard notations for clarity purposes; and iii) the design of a procedure in the form of a toolkit to co-create such models in the LLs. Supplementary material is reported in [4].

II. SOCIO-TECHNICAL PROCESS MODELLING METHOD

In this section, we provide a synthesis of the method described in our previous study [14]; interested readers are invited to read it for a deeper understanding. The proposed method consists of: (i) a set of MoDRE notations to describe the elements of interest linked with a process transformation after the introduction of digital technology; (ii) a procedure to collect the required information and to create the models.

A. Models

To ensure completeness, we model the transformation of a process focusing on three complementary dimensions:

- **Structure:** the UML class diagram [3] provides an overview of the process structure, i.e. actors, resources, tools, and infrastructures involved in the process to-be and the relationships among them.
- **Goal:** the iStar diagram models the goals of the process to-be focusing on the intentional, social, and strategic dimensions [19];
- **Process:** the BPMN diagram [2], [8], [18] represents the detailed flow of the process, including actors' tasks, procedures, and communication. Multiple diagrams are developed to represent both the process as-is and the process to-be. An overlapping visualisation allows comparisons between the overall process before (as-is) and after (to-be) the introduction of the digital technology.

B. Procedure

The procedure is composed of the following steps:

- 1) **Input data collection:** In this phase, information about the process transformed by digital technology is captured through interaction with LL stakeholders in farm visits, interviews, focus groups, etc.
- 2) **Formalisation:** The captured information, enriched with background knowledge, is used by experts to design the diagrams. Interactions with software engineers are foreseen to ensure that the diagrams are syntactically and semantically correct.
- 3) **Feedback collection:** The diagrams are presented to domain experts in the context of a focus group. Additional loops of iteration can be introduced to validate the diagrams.

III. PILOT STUDY

As anticipated, we selected as pilot study the case of an orchard farm introducing a precision irrigation system. The study has been conducted between July and November 2022 in collaboration with "Illuminati Frutta"¹ in Arezzo, Italy. The

adoption of a precision irrigation system has been fueled by its potential in terms of economic, productive, and environmental benefits [17]. After a first round of data collection, we developed a set of diagrams and organised focus groups to evaluate the artefacts. The evaluation of the pilot study helped us to complete and refine both the results and the method. In parallel with a field experiment conducted by researchers from the University of Pisa, the farm owner and the research team are interested in understanding the impacts of the introduction of the precision irrigation system on the business process carried out on the farm. Specifically, the stakeholders need a clear view of the process reengineering after the introduction of the digital system.

A. The Precision Irrigation System

The digital solution in use has evolved over time. The first system, operational from 2019 to 2021, consisted of Drill and Drop probes (by Sentek Inc) for soil moisture sensing, organised in a Wireless Sensor Network (WSN), and of its software counterpart, a decision support system (DSS) named AgriNET developed by Tuctronics. The sensors are capable of real-time data collection at six different soil depths (0-10 cm, 10-20 cm, 20-30 cm, 30-40 cm, and 50-60 cm). Each sensor node operates autonomously, powered by solar energy. Gathered data are sent to a central server via cellular connectivity for storage in a SQL-compliant database. Such data are accessible to users for logging and analysis purposes. Communication among the nodes and the master transceiver occurs via a serial/Ethernet interface. The master transceiver relies on a dedicated gateway to access Internet via cellular networks.

In 2022, a new system, namely "IrriMAX Live" (by Sentek Inc), has been introduced in place of the old one. More advanced than the previous one, it features enhanced logic, particularly regarding node independence in data transmission, parameter management, and firmware updates for connected soil moisture sensors. Users can access data using a web-based interface, IrriMAX Live, or a locally deployable instance, IrriMAX Desktop. Soil moisture dynamics at various depths are available, along with synoptic information related to irrigation quantities and root water uptake. This logic allows for root localization and assessment of the effectiveness of irrigation in capturing the soil volume occupied by the root system.

B. Case study design

We now present the steps of the data collection procedure.

1) *Farm Visit and Data Collection:* The authors of the paper (software engineers and agronomists) visited the farm on July 19, 2022 and spent half a day interacting with workers, agronomists, and the farm's owners. After the visit, the agronomists sent us additional textual material (see supplementary material). The data collected in this phase aims at describing the digital process currently under development that foresees the introduction of a Smart Irrigation System and the changes it is bringing to the farm.

¹<http://www.illuminatifrutta.it> last visited 10 June 2024

2) *Formalisation*: Based on the input data, the first author created the formal diagrams, and the other authors revised them and provided feedback according to their expertise. The phase of internal revision led to eleven changes to better comply with the grammar of the notations and user experience.

Fig. 1 shows a subset of the diagrams we developed. In particular, Fig. 1a contains the UML class diagram with a detailed view of the actors and resources involved in the process and their relationships. The new classes introduced by digital technology are in light blue. In Fig. 1b, the iStar diagram represents the goals, activities and strategical relationships of the farmer interacting with the precision irrigation system. Fig. 1c shows two BPMN models overlapped: a first diagram describing the process of irrigation carried out by the farmer before the introduction of technology, and a second diagram representing the new process introduced by the digital system. In the picture, the new participants, activities and gateways introduced by the technology are in blue; in green the activities and gateways that do not change; in red the activities and gateways that are not present anymore.

3) *Feedback Collection*: The diagrams have been used to further clarify some aspects of the system in a focus group with the agronomists. The focus group for the evaluation of the pilot study was held on November 9, 2022. Six participants took part in the focus group; the group was composed of four males and two females, two experts in agricultural economics (P1 and P2), an agronomist (P3) and three software engineers, with expertise in formal notations (P4), agritech (P5), and user interfaces (P6). The software engineers moderated the discussion. During the focus groups, together with the revision of the diagrams, three questions were asked about the completeness, comprehensibility and effectiveness of the representations. The evaluation led to substantial changes in the diagrams.

4) *Data Analysis*: The data analysis consisted of a thematic analysis [7] of the transcriptions of the focus groups with experts. It was performed by the first author, and the fifth author revised it for understandability and coherence with the transcripts.

IV. RESULTS

This section presents the results obtained from the thematic analysis. For each type of diagram, namely UML, iStar and BPMN, two main aspects were discussed related to the understandability and effectiveness of the representations. A table with the themes that emerged from the thematic analysis is available in our supplementary material.

A. Structure Diagram UML

a) *UML Understandability*: The feedback on understandability confirmed that participants in the focus group agreed that the diagram was clear (P1). However, a few difficulties emerged regarding the *interpretation of hard symbols*. Some participants found it difficult to interpret specific elements of the notation, such as the different types of association connectors, the direction of a few arrows, and the role of attributes. Regarding the latter, P1, while referring to the class

Irrigation tool asked: “What do id and coords mean?”. Such feedback brought us, in a later stage, to avoid using attributes and opt instead for a simpler representation using class names only.

b) *UML Effectiveness*: In general, the participants agreed that the diagram is “very effective” (P1). To assess effectiveness, participants considered potential usage scenarios for this type of diagram in the context of the planned LLs activities and agreed that this diagram is *useful for comparison*. Referring to process modelling activities carried out in parallel in different LLs, P1 affirmed: “It could be useful for every one of us to see the differences among LLs”. Second, a reflection on the role of the diagram in support of business analysts suggested that the diagram can be a *support for cost-benefit analysis*, providing a clear comprehension of the system’s structure. P1 said: “The diagram can help to identify the critical points for the costs”.

B. Goal Diagram iStar

a) *iStar Understandability*: P4 found the diagrams to be communicative enough. The following discussion with all the participants confirmed that they could follow the high-level notation in use and thus provide feedback on the diagram. They agreed to *keep the representation simple*. In fact, being the goal model focused on strategic aspects, the representation should be limited to a small set of actors who are internal to the process: “We should keep it as simple as possible” (P4). Furthermore, some participants had some difficulties with a few symbols. This resulted in the theme *interpretation of hard symbols*, albeit much less evident than the issues highlighted with the UML diagram.

b) *iStar Effectiveness*: The participants evaluated the diagram as effective in presenting the relevant information and communicating it to stakeholders. The diagram was evaluated as extremely useful for *early discussions on strategic aspects*. The participants appreciated a representation focused on a restricted group of actors, but then additional opportunities were discussed and caught their interest. On the one hand, it was agreed that this representation should be limited to a small set of actors who are internal to the process: “We should keep it as simple as possible”, recommended P4; on the other hand, while discussing the possibility to represent the environment as an actor, it was agreed how powerful could be a representation including the environment as an actor and water as a resource provided by it. On this point, P1 commented: “Introducing nature as an actor would support us in the analysis of environmental costs”. However, the final group decision was to *limit the number of actors* in favour of understandability.

C. Process Diagram BPMN

a) *BPMN Understandability*: Participants agreed that the representation is very clear. Furthermore, they discussed the theme *useful colouring*. In fact, they particularly appreciated the overlapped representation enabled by the use of different colours (see Fig. 1c).

(a) UML class diagram

(b) iStar goal diagram

(c) Overlap of BPMN diagrams representing process as-is (green and red) and process to-be (green and blue)

Fig. 1: Models depicting an irrigation process, being transformed by the introduction of a Smart Irrigation System.

b) BPMN Effectiveness: All participants particularly appreciated the overlapping view (see again Fig. 1c) and evaluated it as particularly effective in *presenting the process transformation*. Reasoning on possible usage scenarios, P1 summarised the *multiple objectives of the representation*: “These representations have at least two purposes because one can see the scientific purpose, as for instance with cost analysis; but then they could also be useful for demonstrations, maybe in a simpler version. An interesting companion to demonstrations in the field”.

D. Process Modelling Method

A final time slot in the focus groups was dedicated to a common discussion about the proposed method. Participants confirmed that the models are overall rather complete, effective, and detailed. Furthermore, when discussing scenarios of application of the diagrams, the main theme was the possibility to adopt process models as a *tool for analysis*, especially oriented to reflect on costs and benefits. Moreover, participants also agreed on the *effectiveness of visual representations* compared to the use of text. One last concern was related to the need to set up a common *procedure for the co-creation of the*

diagrams. All participants agreed that it could be a challenging task for LLs because experts in the notation are required. During the meeting, the participants discussed a preliminary procedure proposal based on guidelines to be used by LL coordinators and a template for data collection.

V. DISCUSSION AND ROADMAP

The outcome of the thematic analysis confirms that the participants evaluate the models as effective and understandable, overall speaking. Furthermore, the representations are useful to foster discussion and thus facilitate the stakeholders in identifying incompleteness issues, leading in the end to more representative models. The overall feedback on the method is positive, confirming the willingness of the participants to use the method as an analysis tool and a companion to technology demonstration.

A. Feedback on the models

Regarding the models, the feedback received in the focus group allowed us to identify the main challenges and refine the method according to the solutions commonly agreed upon. A major concern is the need to familiarise with the notation

in order to understand the diagrams thoroughly. Furthermore, some participants had found some difficulties in decoding fine-grained symbols on the diagrams. Thus, a negotiation has been carried out among the authors and the agronomists to simplify the notations by limiting the number of symbols in use while maintaining the completeness of the representations and compliance with the standards (see different versions in supplementary material). For example, a solution adopted in the UML diagram is to highlight in blue both the technological system and components and possibly place the technological elements in the centre of the diagram instead of at a marginal position in order to have an immediate view of the technology in use. A similar solution was adopted for the iStar diagram; in fact, in addition to the use of an aesthetically enhanced notation that was proposed by the authors since the first iteration, it was decided to represent the technology introduced in the system within an actor boundary placed in a central position. Generally, it has been agreed that multiple iterations help to improve the diagrams and identify optimal solutions. This is especially the case of BPMN, which requires input data directly from practitioners involved in the process.

B. Feedback on the procedure

Regarding the procedure, the discussion provided a roadmap for future work. The main concern related to the applicability of the method in CODECS is the need to coordinate the data collection with other project activities and limit the interactions with the LLs to avoid overburdening them. In fact, it is unfeasible for the authors (software engineers) to perform on-field visits in all the 20 LLs and carry out the data collection by interacting directly with stakeholders, also because of the different national languages in use. Furthermore, as confirmed by the procedure used in the pilot study, data collection is an activity that requires a strict collaboration with domain experts so to elicit the necessary information to create the models. Another point to consider is the request for a method easy to follow, to be applied by agronomists in different contexts. Thus, after an accurate evaluation, we went forward with a method based on the co-creation of the models so that each LL can carry out the activities on its own. In addition, we identified three additional artefacts to complete the process modelling toolkit: (i) a guideline document providing a template for data collection; (ii) a checklist to evaluate the completeness of the collected data, highlighting potential inconsistencies; (iii) a procedure to create the diagrams based on the process followed in the pilot study. We are continuing our work on the toolkit, which will be finalised in the upcoming project stages.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented the ongoing progresses in the context of the HE CODECS project. The activity is focused on the development of a method for socio-technical process modelling in agricultural LLs. Starting from a preliminary proposal based on a set of diagrams from MoDRE field, i.e., UML class diagrams, iStar and BPMN, the method has been applied to

a pilot study in the context of a precision irrigation use case and validated in a focus group with agronomists. The results show that the participants consider the models effective and understandable. The active participation in the focus groups showed that not only the agronomists clearly understand the notations and provide feedback, but that they have a critical role in the successful creation of the models. The information collected allowed the fine tuning of the representations in a way effective for the CODECS community. Furthermore, the discussion allowed us to enrich the toolkit for co-creating the diagrams. The toolkit is composed of a set of guidelines for eliciting process-relevant information from LLs, a checklist and a detailed procedure for the creation of the diagrams. The toolkit will be used by the 20 LLs of the CODECS project.

REFERENCES

- [1] Codecs. <https://www.horizoncodecs.eu/>, accessed: 11-17-2023
- [2] Business process model and notation (BPMN) v2.0. <https://www.omg.org/spec/BPMN/2.0/> (2010), accessed: 11-17-2023
- [3] Unified modeling language (UML) 2.5.1 core specification. <https://www.omg.org/spec/UML/> (2017), accessed: 11-17-2023
- [4] Supplementary material for "towards a toolkit for socio-technical process modelling in agriculture: a pilot study". <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12187303> (2024), accessed: 06-20-2024
- [5] Assar, S.: Model driven requirements engineering: Mapping the field and beyond. In: 2014 IEEE MoDRE (2014)
- [6] Beaudoin, C., Joncoux, S., Jasmin, J.F., Berberi, A., McPhee, C., Schillo, R.S., Nguyen, V.M.: A Research agenda for Evaluating Living Labs as an Open Innovation Model for Environmental and Agricultural Sustainability. *Environmental Challenges* **7**, 100505 (2022). <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envc.2022.100505>, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2667010022000658>
- [7] Braun, V., Clarke, V.: Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative research in psychology* **3**(2), 77–101 (2006)
- [8] Corradini, F., Ferrari, A., Fornari, F., Gnesi, S., Polini, A., Re, B., Spagnolo, G.O.: A Guidelines framework for understandable BPMN models. *Data & Knowledge Engineering* **113**, 129–154 (2018)
- [9] da Silveira, F., da Silva, S.L.C., Machado, F.M., Barbedo, J.G.A., Amaral, F.G.: Farmers' perception of the barriers that hinder the implementation of agriculture 4.0. *Agricultural Systems* **208** (2023)
- [10] Doerr, J., Hess, A., Koch, M.: RE and Society - A Perspective on RE in Times of Smart Cities and Smart Rural Areas. In: RE'18. *IEEE* (2018)
- [11] Ferrari, A., Bacco, M., Gaber, K., Jedlitschka, A., Hess, S., Kaipainen, J., Koltsida, P., Toli, E., Brunori, G.: Drivers, Barriers and Impacts of Digitalisation in Rural Areas from the Viewpoint of Experts. *IST* **145**, 106816 (2022)
- [12] Hossain, M., Leminen, S., Westerlund, M.: A systematic review of living lab literature. *Journal of Cleaner Production* **213**, 976–988 (2019)
- [13] Mannari, C., Bacco, M., Ferrari, A., Ortolani, L., Lai, M.B., Mignani, C., Silvi, A., Malizia, A., Brunori, G.: A methodology for process modelling in living labs to foster agricultural digitalisation. In: 2023 IEEE MetroAgriFor (2023)
- [14] Mannari, C., Spagnolo, G.O., Bacco, M., Malizia, A.: Digitalisation of agriculture: Development and evaluation of a model-based requirements engineering process. In: REFSQ 2023 - Posters and Tools (2023)
- [15] Rijswijk, K., Klerkx, L., Bacco, M., Bartolini, F., Bulten, E., Debryne, L., Desein, J., Scotti, I., Brunori, G.: Digital Transformation of Agriculture and Rural Areas: a Socio-Cyber-Physical System Framework to Support Responsibilisation. *JRS* (2021)
- [16] Ryan, M., Isakhanyan, G., Tekinerdogan, B.: An interdisciplinary approach to artificial intelligence in agriculture. *NJAS* **25**, 1–31 (01 2023)
- [17] Sportelli, M., Bonzi, L., Brunori, G., Hamouda, F., Puig-Sirera, A., Marasco, S., Rallo, G.: Current state of irrigation decision support systems (idss) in italy: Critical insights. In: 2023 IEEE MetroAgriFor (2023)
- [18] Van Der Aalst, W.: Process mining: discovery, conformance and enhancement of business processes, vol. 2. Springer (2011)
- [19] Yu, E., Giorgini, P., Maiden, N., Mylopoulos, J., Fickas, S.: *Social Modeling for Requirements Engineering*. The MIT Press (2011)